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Əliyeva S.H., Hüseynov Q.M. Hidrokimyəvi metodla Tl_3SbS_4 birləşməsinin alınması.....	315
Rzayeva S. M. EPR spectra and structural peculiarities of high-density polyethylene films with incorporated InP/Ge particles.....	317
Mammadova T.N. Red emitting CaS:Eu phosphor for white LEDs.....	318
Gulieva T.M. Composites based on polypropylene and high pressure polyethylene with metal-containing nano-fillers.....	320
Ghoghoberidze V., Kakulia D., Lomia A., Tavkheldze A. Density of quantum states in periodical structures.....	322
Ahadova A., Mammadov S. Thermoluminescence dating of ceramic from polutepe archaeological SiTe.....	323
Babayeva A.A. Qamma-kvantlarla şüalandırılmış $TlGaTe_2$ kristallarında ion keçiriciliyi.....	324
Valizade A.H., Popov E., Mirzayev M.N., Demir E., Mirzayeva D.M. Defects formation in the W-VC-C compounds under helium ions irradiation.....	325
Gərayeva A.H., Sadigova N.V., Hüseynova A.A., Məmmədli A.H., Süleymanova N.Y. Method for determining the breakdown voltage of avalanche photodiodes.....	326
Ahmadova G.B. Atomic force microscopy and X-ray diffraction study of high-density polyethylene composites with semiconductor fillers GaAs and GaAs <Te>.....	328
Atakishiyeva J. Application potential of boron carbide nanoparticles on the nuclear and nanotechnology.....	329
Abbasova L. S. Investigation of antibacterial properties of composite materials based on acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene.....	330
Jahangirov M.M., Hajieva S.A. Influence of thermal annealing on photoelectrical properties of GaSe monocrystals were implanted protons.....	331
Abbasov N. Boron nitride nanoparticles as dielectrics for future generation nanoelectronic devices.....	333
Arzumanova N. Properties of nanocomposites based on polyolefins and mineral fillers obtained in solution mixing process.....	334
Məmmədov R.A. InTe birləşməsinin elektrofiziki xassələri.....	335
Vahabova V.Ə. Metakriloilmorfolin və metilmetakrilat əsasında birgə polimerin sintezi və tədqiqi.....	336

THERMOLUMINESCENCE DATING OF CERAMIC FROM POLUTEPE ARCHAEOLOGICAL SITE

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In our previous report [1] the radiocarbon dating method was used to date the age of a charcoal sample from the Polutepe archeological site in the Jalilabad district of Azerbaijan. Polutepe is the largest Neolithic-Eneolithic monument in the Caucasus. A charcoal sample excavated at the Polutepe site was dated by the conventional radiocarbon method at 4270 ± 160 BC, which agrees with the stratigraphic estimated dates. In this work we present the results of our investigations on dating of pottery artifacts found in Polutepe archaeological site by applying the thermoluminescence dating method with the purpose of contributing to the knowledge of the Neolithic period in Azerbaijan. Quartz inclusion method

Figure. The dependency of TL intensity at 375°C peak from the additional laboratory dose.

is employed for the TL dating. The quartz samples used in this experiment were extracted from ceramic using conventional chemical separation. Crashed ceramic sample was sieved into grain size fractions of 80 to 120 μm . This grain size fraction was then treated with HCl, separated by heavy liquids and etched in 40% HF; finally, HCl was used to dissolve precipitated fluorides. The samples were heated up to 600°C for one hour to eliminate any residual TL centers before the subsequent irradiation. The irradiation was performed at an ambient temperature from ^{60}Co source at different dose levels. The

irradiated samples were weighed to 5 ± 0.5 mg and read out after one day in a N_2 atmosphere in a Harshaw 3500 manual reader using the linear heating rate of 20°C/s.

Plotting the TL glow-curve intensity at 375°C against the dose adsorbed and backward extrapolation enables the estimation of historical dose equal to 22.19 ± 1.36 Gy.

Soil sample collected from the close proximity of the pottery sample was air dried and kept in a closed environment for one month. The concentration of U, Th, and K were 2.24 ± 0.20 ppm, 8.31 ± 0.80 ppm, $2.39 \pm 0.23\%$ respectively. Dose rate and age calculation were conducted using the DRAC version 1.2 and output results are as follows: Environmental dose rate: 3.46 ± 0.19 Gy/ka and; Age of the sample: 4.400 ± 530 BC years which are in line with the stratigraphically estimated age of this area and with the radiocarbon age reported in our previous work.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. I. Akhundov, S. G. Mammadov, A. A. Ahadova, and A. N. Abdullayev, "Dating of Charcoal Samples from the Polutepe Archeological Site in Azerbaijan," 2018.